

AVAILABILITY, ACCESSIBILITY AND AFFORDABILITY OF COMMONLY PRESCRIBED ANTIBIOTICS AMONG GENERAL PUBLIC IN TWIN CITIES OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Access to essential antibiotics remains a significant challenge in low and middle income countries, where high medicine costs and inconsistent availability can limit effective treatment. In Pakistan, out of pocket expenditure on medicines is substantial, often forcing patients to compromise on prescribed therapies. This study aimed to evaluate the accessibility, availability and affordability of commonly prescribed antibiotics in Twin cities of Pakistan. *Methodology:* A cross-sectional study was conducted among 300 participants, Data were collected on socio-demographic characteristics, pharmacy access and availability of prescribed medicines and affordability was assessed using WHO/HAI method by calculating the number of days' wages required to complete a standard treatment course. *Results:* Most participants reported reasonable physical access to pharmacies, with a short travel and waiting time, while prescribed medicines were available for the majority, a considerable proportion experienced non-availability due to stock-outs, absence of specific prescribed brands or dosage forms. Affordability emerged as a major concern, with two-thirds of participants unable to afford their prescribed treatment. A strong association was observed between household income and affordability, with individuals earning below PKR 70,000/month facing the greatest difficulty. *Conclusion:* The findings indicate that affordability, rather than physical access or availability, is the primary barrier to appropriate antibiotic use in this population.

Introduction

Access to essential medicines is a critical component of effective healthcare delivery, particularly in low and middle income countries like Pakistan, where medicines often constitute a major portion of household expenditure (1-4) High medicine prices often make them unaffordable, especially for people with lower incomes, leading

them to either skip treatment or purchase incomplete courses. This not only worsens health outcomes but also contributes to the rise of antimicrobial resistance, a growing public health threat worldwide(5, 6) Antibiotics, in particular, are critical for managing bacterial infections, but their misuse or incomplete consumption accelerates AMR, making effective treatment more

difficult and expensive (7-9) In Pakistan, patients frequently rely on private pharmacies because medicines are often unavailable in government facilities, pushing families toward higher out of pocket expenses(10, 11) World Health Organization introduced the Essential Medicines List (EML) in 1977 to ensure that safe, effective and cost-effective medicines are available for the public use (12). To guide rational antibiotic use and limit AMR, WHO later categorized antibiotics into Access, Watch and Reserve group in 2017(13, 14) Research in Pakistan indicates that the availability of key access antibiotics in private pharmacies is far from ideal. For instance, originator brands were present in just 45.2% of surveyed outlets, while lowest priced generics were available in 40.2% (15) Certain antibiotics like Cefazolin, Chloramphenicol, Cloxacillin, Nitrofurantion and Phenoxymethylpenicillin and streptomycin were completely absent, whereas Co-amoxiclav, Clarithromycin, Metronidazole, Azithromycin and Ciprofloxacin were more consistently available.(15) Affordability remains another major challenge. Several originator brands, including ceftriaxone and ciprofloxacin are priced significantly higher than international reference levels. When treatment costs were compared with the daily wage of the lowest paid government workers, standard courses of ciprofloxacin and cefotaxime often exceed a full day's wage, making them unaffordable for many (15). On the other hand, antibiotics such as Amoxicillin, Doxycycline and Metronidazole were generally affordable. This combination of low availability and high cost can result in patients starting therapy but being unable to complete it, ultimately promoting misuse and resistance.

Considering the rising burden of infections in Urban centers such as Islamabad and Rawalpindi, it is crucial to assess how readily the general public can access commonly prescribed antibiotics, evaluating availability, affordability and accessibility in these cities will highlight critical gaps, inform policies and support strategies to ensure rational antibiotics use, thereby improving treatment outcomes and helping curb AMR in Pakistan.

Methodology

Study Design and Settings

This was a cross-sectional study conducted among the general public visiting 60 community pharmacies in twin cities of Pakistan, Islamabad and Rawalpindi. A total of 60 pharmacies were surveyed, including 20 in Islamabad and 40 in Rawalpindi, selected to capture a representative sample of community pharmacy settings in Twin cities.

Participants included adult patients or their caregivers who visited the selected pharmacies to purchase antibiotics during the study period. Individuals who refused consent or were visiting for non-antibiotic medicines were excluded. A total of approximately 300 participants were included, using a consecutive sampling method to ensure coverage of different demographic and socio-economic backgrounds

Data were collected using a structured, self-developed proforma divided into 4 sections: Demographics including Age, Gender, Occupation, Monthly household income, Accessibility including Pharmacy location, distance to pharmacy, travel-time, transportation cost, waiting time at pharmacy, Availability and Non-availability of Antibiotics including reasons of non-availability and Affordability of Antibiotics as ratio of daily income to medicine cost. The proforma was validated prior to data collection through a Pilot study and reviewed by experts in Pharmacy Practice, ensuring content validity, Clarity and Feasibility.

Trained Data collectors approached eligible participants at pharmacies, explained the study objectives and obtained informed consent. Data were recorded directly from patient interactions and medicine labels to ensure accuracy. Pharmacy visits were conducted during business hours and the survey captured real-time availability, Pricing and Accessibility measures.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27. Descriptive statistics summarized demographics, pharmacy accessibility and medicine availability and consumer response. Affordability of prescribed antibiotics was assessed both by

consumer-reported perception and using the WHO/HAI methodology, calculating days' wages required for a full course of treatment. $\text{Affordability} = \frac{\text{Daily household income (PKR/day)}}{\text{Total treatment cost per patient (PKR)}}$. Associations between affordability and demographic factors (income and occupation) were evaluated using Chi-square tests, with Phi, Cramer's V, Pearson's R and Spearman's correlation to measure the strength of relationships. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 300 participants were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 43.45 ± 13.87 years, with an age range of 18 to 65 years. The gender distribution was nearly equal, with 149 (49.7%) males and 151 (50.3%) females. Regarding Occupation, the largest proportion of participants were laborers (22.0%) followed by auto drivers (14.3%) housewives (14.3%), students (13.7%), corporate employees (12.7%), government employees (12.7%) and taxi drivers (10.3%). In terms of monthly household income, 35.0% of participants earned between PKR 50,000 to 70,000, 33.3% between PKR 70,000 to 100,000 and 31.7% earned less than PKR 50,000.

Accessibility indicators showed that 48% of participants had a pharmacy located within 1 km,

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of participants and key indicators of accessibility, availability, and affordability of prescribed medicines

VARIABLE	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENT (%)
AGE (YEARS)	Mean \pm SD	43.45 ± 13.87	Range 18-65
GENDER	Male	149	49.7
	Female	151	50.3
OCCUPATION	Laborer	66	22.0
	Auto Driver	43	14.3
	Housewife	43	14.3
	Student	41	13.7
	Corporate Employee	38	12.7
	Government Employee	38	12.7
	Taxi Driver	31	10.3
	MONTHLY HOUSEHOLD INCOME (PKR)	<50,000	95
	50,000-70,000	105	35.0

while 52% reported a distance of 1-1.5 km. Travel time to pharmacies was generally short to moderate. The largest proportion of participants 39.3% reported a travel time of 10 to 15 minutes, followed by 31.7% who reached a pharmacy within 5 to 10 minutes and 29.0% who required 15 to 20 minutes. The cost of transportation was on average 100 PKR across all participants. Waiting time at Pharmacies was relatively short, with 81.5% of participants waiting less than 10 minutes and 19.5% waiting between 10 to 20 minutes.

Overall, 68% of participants reported that all prescribed medicines were available at the pharmacy, while 32.0% experienced non-availability, the most commonly reported reasons for non-availability of medicines included; Out of Stock at the Pharmacy (11.7%), Non-Availability of specific prescribed brand (11.3%) and Non-Availability in required dosage form (9.0%). In such case of medicine non-availability, Consumers alternate response included Buying medicines from another pharmacy (10.0%), Skipping Purchase (9.0%), Substituting with alternatives (7.3%) and Delaying purchase (5.7%).

About the affordability of Medicines, Only 33.3% of participants were categorized as being able to afford prescribed medicines, while a significant majority 66.7% were classified as unable to afford their prescribed medications.

PHARMACY DISTANCE	70,000–100,000	100	33.3
	Within 1 km	144	48.0
	1–1.5 km	156	52.0
TRAVEL TIME TO PHARMACY	5–10 min	95	31.7
	10–15 min	118	39.3
TRANSPORTATION COST (PKR)	15–20 min	87	29.0
	Mean ± SD	100 ± 0	–
WAITING TIME AT PHARMACY	<10 min	152	50.7
	10–20 min	148	49.3
AVAILABILITY OF ALL MEDICINES	Yes	204	68.0
	No	96	32.0
REASONS FOR NON-AVAILABILITY	Out of stock	35	11.7
	Non-availability of specific brand	34	11.3
	Non-availability in required dosage form	27	9.0
	Bought from another pharmacy	30	10.0
CONSUMER RESPONSE TO NON-AVAILABILITY	Skipped purchase	27	9.0
	Substituted with alternatives	22	7.3
	Delayed purchase	17	5.7
AFFORDABILITY OF MEDICINES	Affordable	100	33.3
	Not Affordable	200	66.7

Availability and Affordability of Medicines

Chi-square analyses revealed no significant associations between monthly household income and Availability of prescribed medicines. The findings indicate that income did not influence participant's physical access to pharmacies or the availability of medicines, suggesting that financial barriers, rather than geographic or logistic factors could be the primary determinants of affordability. A chi-square test revealed a strong and statistically significant association between monthly household income and affordability of prescribed medicines ($\chi^2 = 300.0$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$), specifically; Participants earning less than PKR 70,000 per month were universally unable to afford prescribed medicines, while only those participants earning PKR 70,000 to 100,000 per month reported that

they could afford their prescribed medicines. Measures of association indicated a very strong effect, with Phi and Cramer's V both equal to 1.0 and a linear correlation of Pearson's $R = 0.863$ and Spearman's $\rho = 0.866$, highlighting that income is a near to perfect determinant of affordability in this population.

Affordability of prescribed antibiotics was also analyzed in relation to participant's occupations. Cross tabulation showed that affordability varied across occupational groups; the highest proportion of participants reporting treatment as not affordable were laborers (74.2%), followed by auto-drivers (60.5%) and housewives (62.8%) while corporate employees (47.4%) and students (34.1%) had relatively higher affordability. However, the association between occupation and affordability

was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 8.898$, $df = 6$, $p = 0.179$), indicating that while some occupational differences exist descriptively, occupation alone did not significantly influence the likelihood of being able to afford treatment in this population.

In Addition to frequencies and cross-tabulation results, The Affordability of commonly prescribed antibiotics was assessed using WHO/HAI methodology (World Health Organization & Health Action International, 2018), calculating the number of days' wages required for a full course of treatment.

$$\text{Affordability} = \frac{\text{Total treatment Cost Per Patient (PKR)}}{\text{Daily Household Income (PKR)}}$$

The total minimum treatment cost per patient was estimated at approximately PKR 1,999 which included the average antibiotic cost (PKR 699), analgesic/antipyretic medications (PKR 200), basic

Table 2: *Affordability of prescribed antibiotic treatment across different household income groups, expressed as daily income, total treatment cost, and number of days' wages required (WHO/HAI methodology).*

HOUSEHOLD INCOME (PKR/MONTH)	DAILY INCOME (PKR/DAY)	TREATMENT COST (PKR)	DAYS' WAGES	AFFORDABILITY
<50,000	1,667	1,999	1.2	Not affordable
50,000–70,000	1,667–2,333	1,999	0.86–1.2	Borderline
70,000–100,000	2,333–3,333	1,999	0.60–0.86	Affordable

Discussions

This study highlights that economic constraints are the predominant barrier to appropriate antibiotic use in the community, overshadowing physical accessibility and pharmacy availability. The findings in this study aligns with prior studies in LMICs reported in different research studies where financial limitations determined whether patients completed antibiotic courses. (1, 3-5) (16, 17) Even when Antibiotics were physically available, individuals with lower household incomes often resorted to partial treatment, delayed purchases or substitution with less effective alternatives. Such practices in resource limited contexts can contribute to treatment failure and the proliferation of antimicrobial resistance (1, 2, 6)

The relationship between income and affordability observed in this study underscores the complex interplay between socioeconomic factors and healthcare utilization.. Similar to some research

laboratory tests advised by consulting physician (PKR 500) and doctor consultation fee (PKR 500) and travel cost of 100 PKR only. Affordability was then calculated as treatment cost divided by household income for each income group. The analysis indicated that treatment exceeded one days' income for households earning less than 50,000 per month, making it unaffordable. For households earning 50,000 to 70,000 PKR/month, treatment cost ranged from slightly above to below one days income, indicating that affordability was marginal or borderline. Whereas households earning 70,000 to 100,000 PKR/month could afford treatment comfortably, as it required less than One day's income. These findings highlight that financial factors, rather than physical access or availability, are the primary barriers to antibiotic use in the study population.

studies, individuals with lower incomes frequently relied on informal medicine suppliers or community drug stores due to perceived or actual cost saving(3, 4) Another study further supports this, emphasizing that households often made medication decisions based on affordability rather than clinical appropriateness, which can exacerbate misuse of antibiotics and increase the likelihood of resistance.(16, 17) Some research study patterns demonstrate that socioeconomic determinants, rather than mere geographic proximity to healthcare facilities or pharmacies, critically influence rational antibiotic use (3-5, 17)

Non-availability of specific medications or dosage forms emerged as another factor influencing patient behavior, promoting alternative strategies such as switching pharmacies, delaying purchase or using substitute drugs. This mirrors findings from many research studies which identified similar adaptive behaviors in LMIC communities (1, 5, 8,

16, 18) Such practices, while understandable, may compromise treatment efficacy, prolong illness and increase the risk of resistance development. Furthermore, reliance on informal or unlicensed providers, common in communities with financial restraints, may lead to inconsistent dosing, inappropriate antibiotic selection or incomplete courses, all of which are key drivers of antimicrobial resistance in these settings (1, 3-5, 17)

A key finding of this study is that individuals earning below PKR 70,000/month were largely unable to afford prescribed treatment. These findings align with the evidence from a recent study which emphasizes that access to essential antibiotics is not solely dependent on physical availability but also on affordability and health system efficiency. The study reported that although private sector pharmacies showed relatively higher availability of antibiotics compared to public sector, overall access remained suboptimal due to systemic and economic constraints (19) Furthermore, research studies identify that lack of availability of first-line antibiotics often forces reliance on alternative, frequently more expensive or inappropriate options, thereby increasing treatment costs and exacerbating financial burden on patients (16)

This indirectly supports the present study's observation that even when medicines are available, patients may still fail to obtain them due to cost-related barriers. There is a structural disparity consistent with broader context of low and middle income countries where affordability and financial protection mechanisms are often insufficient to ensure equitable access to essential medicines. The inability of lower income groups to afford treatment may lead to treatment interruption, delayed care or complete non-adherence, all of which have significant clinical and public health consequences (15)

The non-availability of essential access group antibiotics can push prescribers toward second line antibiotics, when combined with affordability issues, this creates a dual burden; patient either pay more for alternative therapies or forgo treatment altogether, both of which can worsen disease outcomes. The present study's findings strongly

highlights how market-based access without financial protection disproportionately disadvantages lower-income populations. Overall, the study highlights that improving physical access alone is insufficient to ensure equitable healthcare delivery. While a significant proportion of participants reported reasonable proximity to pharmacies and short waiting times, these factors did not translate into effective access due to financial constraints. This underscores the need for integrated policy approaches that simultaneously address medicine pricing, income disparities and health financing mechanisms. This study reinforces that improving affordability through subsidized medications, income-based pricing, or expanded health insurance coverage must be a central strategy. Simultaneously, strengthening supply chains to ensure consistent availability of essential antibiotics, regardless of brand or dosage forms is critical to prevent consumer from seeking alternative or incomplete therapies (3, 5, 8). The findings of this study suggest avenues for future research to examine behavioral drivers behind the selection of alternative therapies when prescriptions are unaffordable or unavailable, as well as the role of informal medicine sellers in antibiotics misuse (3-5, 18)

Conclusion

This study concludes that affordability is the primary barrier to accessing prescribed antibiotics in twin cities; Islamabad and Rawalpindi, of Pakistan particularly among low and lower-middle-income populations. Despite adequate physical access to pharmacies and generally acceptable availability of medicines, individuals with monthly incomes below PKR 70,000 were largely unable to afford treatment. This highlights a critical gap between access and effective utilization of healthcare services.

The findings emphasize that economic constraints, rather than geographic or logistic factors, drive inequities in antibiotic use, leading to delayed treatment, incomplete therapy and potential misuse. Addressing the challenges requires policy interventions focused on reducing out of pocket expenditure, improving affordability of essential medicines and strengthening public sector healthcare systems. Without targeted financial

protection strategies, efforts to improve antibiotic access and combat antimicrobial resistance are unlikely to achieve meaningful and sustainable outcomes.

Future Recommendations

Future research should examine the role of healthcare providers; Physician, Pharmacist and Nurses in managing situations where patient cannot afford prescribed medicines, including prescribing alternatives or advising partial treatments. Understanding these practices can help identify gaps in clinical and dispensing behavior. In addition to that, Research should evaluate the effectiveness of interventions such as subsidized medicines, insurance schemes or pricing regulations in improving antibiotic affordability and adherence, to guide evidence based policy decisions.

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